

1 dataquieR 2: An updated R package for FAIR data
2 quality assessments in observational studies and
3 electronic health record data

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7 **Summary**

8 dataquieR version 2 is a major update to the dataquieR package (Richter et al., 2021), which
9 enables extensive, highly standardized, and accessible data quality assessments related to data
10 integrity (e.g. data type errors, duplicates), completeness (e.g. missing values), consistency
11 (e.g. range violations, contradictions), and accuracy (e.g. outliers, time trends, examiner
12 effects) on tabular form data. This update extends the coverage of data quality indicators
13 from the underlying framework (Schmidt et al., 2021) based on a substantially improved
14 information model, comprises performance enhancements, interactive output, and versatile
15 options to grade data quality issues. The broader framework coverage is achieved by inte-
16 grating dataquieR 2 with a differentiated spreadsheet-type metadata schema. This schema
17 includes descriptions, expectations and requirements about the following data objects in a
18 machine-readable way: (1) single variables and data fields, (2) combinations of variables, (3)
19 segments of the data, (4) data tables, (5) representation and classification of missing data,
20 and (6) identifier codes. The new metadata schema makes additional assumptions underly-
21 ing data quality assessments explicit, thereby improving reproducible data quality reporting
22 in compliance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles
23 (Wilkinson et al., 2016). While dataquieR has primarily been designed for and is currently
24 used in observational health studies, such as population-based cohort studies (Peters et al.,
25 2022; Schmidt et al., 2023), it can also be applied to all sorts of tabular data from other
26 sources, for instance, electronic health record (EHR) data, or registries.

27 **Statement of Need**

28 The need to thoroughly assess data before using them for any substantive scientific purpose
29 is undisputed, and much work has been done in this regard. On the one hand, several data
30 quality frameworks have been developed in the health sciences to guide related assessments.
31 Examples are frameworks with a focus on medical registries (Lee et al., 2017; Nonnemacher
32 et al., 2014), EHR data (Kahn et al., 2016; Liaw et al., 2021; Weiskopf & Weng, 2013),
33 or observational health research data collections (Nonnemacher et al., 2014; Schmidt et al.,
34 2021). Other conceptual work focuses on checking data properties as part of an initial data
35 analysis (Huebner et al., 2018). On the other hand, many tools have been made available to
36 assess data quality in different programming languages (Ehrlinger & Woss, 2022; Mariño et
37 al., 2022). Still, substantial challenges remain; a recent review of 27 R packages to assess data
38 quality revealed important issues (Mariño et al., 2022). The most important drawbacks in most
39 existing R packages for quality evaluation are that these tools are not based on formal data

40 quality frameworks, and the rules underlying the assessments need to be provided in a program-
41 specific syntax rather than being available in an interoperable, reusable format. Exceptions are
42 dataquieR (Richter et al., 2021), and DQAstats (Kapsner et al., 2021). The latter is used for
43 inpatient EHR data, while dataquieR targets designed observational research studies. Despite
44 their different underlying concepts, both define quality-related metadata separately from the
45 programming code. Stand-alone metadata files comprising data descriptions, expectations
46 and requirements are, however, a major precondition to making reproducible data quality
47 assessments (Mariño et al., 2022). Regarding dataquieR, three main shortcomings existed:
48 first, the functions and previous metadata concept only allowed calculating 18 out of 34 data
49 quality indicators from the underlying data quality framework (Schmidt et al., 2021); second,
50 performance issues in handling larger numbers of variables in a single report limited its use;
51 third, even complex output was static, thus limiting the possibility of users to interactively
52 focus on details of concern.

53 New functionalities

54 Metadata is now organized in six tables (formerly two tables) that specify overall expectations
55 at the levels of: (1) single variables and data fields (e.g. range violations of individual data
56 values, expected range of a mean), (2) combinations of variables (e.g. contradictions between
57 values of different variables), (3) segments of the data (e.g. different examinations), (4)
58 data tables (e.g. data from the entire study), (5) representation and classification of missing
59 data (e.g. linking a study specific use of missing value codes with a generic approach (AA-
60 POR, 2023)), and (6) valid identifier codes (e.g. pseudo ids). Each metadata table can be
61 handled as a spreadsheet in a workbook, allowing metadata input directly in the spreadsheet
62 or by specifying the source file for a specific item (e.g. another spreadsheet or a URL). For
63 an easier and more accessible way of annotating complex contradiction rules, dataquieR 2
64 supports a syntax language inspired by REDCap's syntax (Harris et al., 2009). Examples for
65 contradictions in the new syntax are: (1) "[sbp1] < [dbp1]" to indicate that systolic blood
66 pressure cannot be lower than diastolic blood pressure; or (2) "[DIABETES_KNOWN_0] =
67 'yes' and [DIAB_AGE_ONSET_0] = ''" to denote that for study participants with a known
68 diabetes diagnosis, the age of onset of diabetes should also be specified (i.e. cannot be empty).
69 Whereas the earlier approach could only handle the relation of two variables, now there is no
70 formal limit to rule complexity.

71 The metadata extensions enable new indicator functions to discover data quality issues. They
72 foremost target the Integrity and Accuracy dimensions of the guiding framework (Schmidt et
73 al., 2021), comprising new options to detect unexpected data elements or data records, dupli-
74 cates, as well as the detection of unexpected proportion and unexpected location parameters
75 (e.g. mean outside a defined range). Thus, dataquieR 2 allows for the evaluation of 24 data
76 quality indicators out of the 34 in the concept, where the extended metadata scheme already
77 lays the basis for the coverage of the remaining indicators. Another development is classifying
78 data quality issues into up to five categories according to their severity. This grading enables
79 users to obtain a comprehensive overview and identify potentially problematic variables more
80 quickly.

81 Numerous output improvements have been implemented. Examples include Figure 1: (1) a
82 pie chart summarizing the number of variables in each data quality category, (2) a summary
83 matrix displaying all potential data quality issues or problems related to missing/deficient
84 metadata, (3) easier navigation thanks to the inclusion of breadcrumbs that show the current
85 location in the report, (4) more detailed output for specific data quality checks combining
86 tables and interactive plots, (5) the use of hover text in plots to better interpret the results,
87 (6) the possibility to download plots and tables directly from the report as well as to obtain
88 the source code to reproduce plots individually, (7) the inclusion of descriptive statistics and
89 metadata information in the report.

90 dataquieR 2 reports are produced using a two-stage approach: computation and rendering.
 91 First, the computation stage creates a list with all possible and reasonable function calls
 92 according to the metadata. These independent functions are executed in parallel. We elimi-
 93 nated idle times and sequential parts in the report computation through different parallelization
 94 strategies, most prominently, a job-queue-based approach (Bengtsson, 2021, 2023; Csárdi &
 95 Chang, 2022).

96 In the rendering stage, reports are no longer produced using R Markdown (Allaire et al.,
 97 2023). dataquieR 2 directly renders HTML files using htmltools (Cheng et al., 2023), which
 98 speeds up the reporting and improves the use of HTML-specific capabilities (e.g. interactive
 99 figures using plotly (Sievert, 2020)). Importantly, dataquieR 2 does not write single large
 100 files containing all required resources but creates a complete mini-website for the data quality
 101 report, which can be displayed by web browsers using fewer resources of the client computer
 102 (i.e. in terms of memory and CPU usage).

Figure 1: Outline of dataquieR 2's report, showing the main sections with selected outputs for each case.

103 Installation and examples

104 dataquieR 2 is available on the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) and can be installed
 105 using `install.packages("dataquieR")`.

106 Example 1: Computing a data quality report

```
library(dataquieR)

report_ship_data <- dq_report2(
  study_data = "ship",
  meta_data_v2 = "ship_meta_v2",
```

```

dimensions = NULL,
label_col = LONG_LABEL,
title = "SHIP data quality report"
)

```

```
print(report_ship_data, dir = "~/data_quality_reports/report_ship_data")
```

107 The resulting report is available at https://dataquality.qihs.uni-greifswald.de/report_2024q1/

108 Example 2: Calculating a data quality indicator (uncertain and inadmissible numerical values,
109 Figure 2)

```

ship_data <- prep_get_data_frame("ship")

prep_load_workbook_like_file("ship_meta_v2")

sbp1_limits <- con_limit_deviations(
  resp_vars = "sbp1",
  study_data = ship_data
)

sbp1_limits$SummaryPlotList
sbp1_limits$ReportSummaryTable
sbp1_limits$SummaryData

```


Figure 2: Improved output of the `con_limit_deviations` indicator function showing the three possible limits for a variable in a single plot (from Example 2).

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114 References

- 115 AAPOR. (2023). *Standard definitions: Final dispositions of case codes and outcome rates for*
116 *surveys* (10th ed.). The American Association for Public Opinion Research.
- 117 Allaire, J. J., Xie, Y., Dervieux, C., McPherson, J., Luraschi, J., Ushey, K., Atkins, A.,
118 Wickham, H., Cheng, J., Chang, W., & Iannone, R. (2023). *Rmarkdown: Dynamic*
119 *documents for r*. R package version 2.25. <https://github.com/rstudio/rmarkdown>
- 120 Bengtsson, H. (2021). A unifying framework for parallel and distributed processing in r using
121 futures. *The R Journal*, 13(2), 273–291. <https://doi.org/10.32614/RJ-2021-048>
- 122 Bengtsson, H. (2023). *Parallely: Enhancing the 'parallel' package*. R package version 1.36.0.
123 <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=parallely>
- 124 Cheng, J., Sievert, C., Schloerke, B., Chang, W., Xie, Y., & Allen, J. (2023). *Htmltools: Tools*
125 *for HTML*. R package version 0.5.7. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=htmltools>
- 126 Csárdi, G., & Chang, W. (2022). *Callr: Call r from r*. R package version 3.7.3. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=callr>
- 128 Ehrlinger, L., & Woss, W. (2022). A survey of data quality measurement and monitoring
129 tools. *Front Big Data*, 5(5), 850611. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2022.850611>
- 130 Harris, P. A., Taylor, R., Thielke, R., Payne, J., Gonzalez, N., & Conde, J. G. (2009). Research
131 electronic data capture (REDCap)—a metadata-driven methodology and workflow process
132 for providing translational research informatics support. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*,
133 42(2), 377–381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2008.08.010>
- 134 Huebner, M., Cessie, S. le, Schmidt, C. O., & Vach, W. (2018). A contemporary conceptual
135 framework for initial data analysis. *Observational Studies*, 4(1), 171–192. <https://doi.org/10.1353/obs.2018.0014>
- 137 Kahn, M. G., Callahan, T. J., Barnard, J., Bauck, A. E., Brown, J., Davidson, B. N., Estiri,
138 H., Goerg, C., Holve, E., Johnson, S. G., Liaw, S. T., Hamilton-Lopez, M., Meeker,
139 D., Ong, T. C., Ryan, P., Shang, N., Weiskopf, N. G., Weng, C., Zozus, M. N., &
140 Schilling, L. (2016). A harmonized data quality assessment terminology and framework
141 for the secondary use of electronic health record data. *EGEMS (Wash DC)*, 4(1), 1244.
142 <https://doi.org/10.13063/2327-9214.1244>
- 143 Kapsner, L. A., Mang, J. M., Mate, S., Seuchter, S. A., Vengadeswaran, A., Bathelt, F., Dep-
144 penwiese, N., Kadioglu, D., Kraska, D., & Prokosch, H. U. (2021). Linking a consortium-
145 wide data quality assessment tool with the MIRACUM metadata repository. *Appl Clin*
146 *Inform*, 12(4), 826–835. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1733847>
- 147 Lee, K., Weiskopf, N., & Pathak, J. (2017). A framework for data quality assessment in
148 clinical research datasets. *AMIA Annu Symp Proc, 2017*, 1080–1089. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29854176>
- 150 Liaw, S. T., Guo, J. G. N., Ansari, S., Jonnagaddala, J., Godinho, M. A., Borelli, A. J.,
151 Lusignan, S. de, Capurro, D., Liyanage, H., Bhattal, N., Bennett, V., Chan, J., & Kahn,
152 M. G. (2021). Quality assessment of real-world data repositories across the data life cycle:
153 A literature review. *J Am Med Inform Assoc*, 28(7), 1591–1599. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa340>
- 155 Mariño, J., Kasbohm, E., Struckmann, S., Kapsner, L. A., & Schmidt, C. O. (2022). R
156 packages for data quality assessments and data monitoring: A software scoping review
157 with recommendations for future developments. *Applied Sciences*, 12(9), 4238. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12094238>

- 159 Nonnemacher, M., Nasseh, D., & Stausberg, J. (2014). *Datenqualität in der medizinischen*
160 *forschung: Leitlinie zum adaptiven management von datenqualität in kohortenstudien und*
161 *registern*. TMF e.V. <https://doi.org/10.32745/9783954663743>
- 162 Peters, A., German National Cohort, C., Peters, A., Greiser, K. H., Gottlicher, S., Ahrens, W.,
163 Albrecht, M., Bamberg, F., Barnighausen, T., Becher, H., Berger, K., Beule, A., Boeing,
164 H., Bohn, B., Bohnert, K., Braun, B., Brenner, H., Bulow, R., Castell, S., ... others.
165 (2022). Framework and baseline examination of the german national cohort (NAKO). *Eur*
166 *J Epidemiol*, 37(10), 1107–1124. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-022-00890-5>
- 167 Richter, A., Schmidt, C. O., Krüger, M., & Struckmann, S. (2021). dataquieR: Assessment of
168 data quality in epidemiological research. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 6(61), 3039.
169 <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03093>
- 170 Schmidt, C. O., Struckmann, S., Enzenbach, C., Reineke, A., Stausberg, J., Damerow, S.,
171 Huebner, M., Schmidt, B., Sauerbrei, W., & Richter, A. (2021). Facilitating harmonized
172 data quality assessments. A data quality framework for observational health research
173 data collections with software implementations in r. *BMC Med Res Methodol*, 21(1), 63.
174 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01252-7>
- 175 Schmidt, C. O., Struckmann, S., Scholz, M., Schossow, J., Radke, D., Richter, A., Reineke,
176 A., Kasbohm, E., Coronado, J. M., Schauer, B., Henselin, K., Westphal, S., Balke, D.,
177 Leddig, T., Volzke, H., & Henke, J. (2023). Conducting an epidemiologic study and
178 making it FAIR: Reusable tools and procedures from a population-based cohort study.
179 *Stud Health Technol Inform*, 302, 871–875. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SHTI230292>
- 180 Sievert, C. (2020). *Interactive web-based data visualization with r, plotly, and shiny*. Chap-
181 man; Hall/CRC.
- 182 Weiskopf, N. G., & Weng, C. (2013). Methods and dimensions of electronic health record
183 data quality assessment: Enabling reuse for clinical research. *J Am Med Inform Assoc*,
184 20(1), 144–151. <https://doi.org/10.1136/amiajnl-2011-000681>
- 185 Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A.,
186 Blomberg, N., Boiten, J. W., Silva Santos, L. B. da, Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes,
187 A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers,
188 R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and
189 stewardship. *Sci Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>